

ISic3654

I.Sicily inscription 3654

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.10.31 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Monte Alburchia di Gangi

Provenance

'nella zona di M. Alburchia', which is

<http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/462327>

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Gangi, Museo Civico di
Gangi

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 199-200 no.3 tav.71.1

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